

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: RUEY****FIRST NAME: TETHLOACH****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (MS Word – 365 on Windows 11)

Concepts covered in this Response Paper:

1. **Academic essay writing** (EUCLID 2021, 6-14)
2. **Punctuation rules, US and UK English disparities** (EUCLID 2021,15-32)
3. **Plagiarism** (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
4. **Writing style** (EUCLID 2021, 40-57)
5. **Latin abbreviations and expressions** (EUCLID 2021, 58-64)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I am writing this response paper based on the Euclid University *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack* and videos provided as part of the *Coursepack*. I found the *Coursepack* to be an invaluable document that will aid me throughout my doctoral studies.

In this response paper, I succinctly discuss academic essay writing, punctuation rules and the United States (US) and United Kingdom (UK) English disparities, plagiarism, writing styles, and Latin abbreviations and expressions.

2) ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

This chapter discusses academic essay writing and how a writer could write an excellent academic essay. Essay writing is a process that a writer must commence as early as possible (James Cook University, n.d., 1). A writer must organize readings on time for the timely completion of research. Early commencement of an essay gives the writer time to edit a paper and consult a tutor or friend to view an essay for advice. Procrastination compromises the time and quality of an essay (EUCLID 2021, 7).

When reading books or writing an essay, it is significant that a writer focuses on the main research topic. Having the main research question in mind avoids confusion because a writer may write contrary to the subject. Furthermore, to clarify the research topic, a writer must always ask critical questions that could broaden creative thinking. Critical questions develop the writer's ideas and help answer critical questions (EUCLID 2021, 7).

3) PUNCTUATION RULES, US AND UK ENGLISH DISPARITIES

This chapter discusses punctuation rules and the US and UK English disparities. Additionally, it outlines when a writer could apply punctuation rules. Generally, “English is a crazy language” (Lederer n.d., 1). Whoever disputes this fact does not know English. Terminologies of diverse ethnicities, for example, Black people, Yiddish, and Jewish, further complicate the English (EUCLID 2021, 30). Besides, punctuation has complex rules. Inserting punctuation in the wrong place can alter the intended meaning of a sentence—for example, using brackets, ellipses, and quotations. Thus, writers should use punctuation appropriately and in consideration of the US-UK English variations (EUCLID 2021, 15-23).

The US and UK English rules are dissimilar. They differ in many ways, especially in punctuation and spelling. Though the US and UK English are popular internationally, US English is the dominant one. The US's global political, military, and economic dominance elevated its English over the UK English (EUCLID 2021, 15-32). The US global power obliges authors to conform to the US English rules.

4) PLAGIARISM

This chapter discusses plagiarism and how to avoid it when writing essays. Plagiarism is an “intellectual theft” (UNSW, n.d., 1), which occurs when a writer uses an author's intellectual work without crediting or acknowledging the author. In academic writing, plagiarism is “unethical” and “dishonesty.” To avoid plagiarism, a writer must acknowledge an author through appropriate in-text citing, quoting, or paraphrasing using the referencing style a faculty recommends (EUCLID 2021, 34-39).

5) WRITING STYLES

This chapter discusses internationally acceptable writing styles. Writing styles are methods writers use to present their ideas. A writer can choose a specific writing style depending on the technicality of the research, the publisher's preference, customer demands, or project demand (EUCLID 2021, 41).

Euclid University recommends the Turabian (Chicago) rules and the US English writing style (EUCLID 2021, 41). The US English has rules different from the UK English rules. Significantly, a writer should pay attention to the rules, especially spelling, syntax, or punctuation, of the chosen English. Some words frequently confuse writers or readers, such as compound words, quotation marks, prefixes, or words that should be in italics.

6) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

This chapter discusses the use of Latin abbreviations and expressions in academic essays. Writing styles consider Latin abbreviations and expressions writers use when writing academic papers. The reason authors apply Latin abbreviations and expressions in English writings is that English needs more vocabulary to express the intended meaning of a word. However, some writers use them to make their points “sound more sophisticated and scholarly” (University of North Carolina n.d., 1). It is wise to omit them in writing if they cannot convey the intended meaning of an expression. They can confuse or are challenging to understand.

7) CONCLUSION

In sum, the EUCLID *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* is a perfect guide for students to write an academic essay or a professional paper. It discusses how to write a good essay on time. An excellent academic essay appropriately applies punctuation, understands the US and UK English variations, is plagiarism-free, and consistently contains the recommended writing style rules. Though EUCLID recommends Turabian and US English in essay writing, a writer can use any internationally acceptable writing style or UK English. However, a writer must be consistent throughout the essay with the style of choice. The *Coursepack* is an excellent guide I am happy to use throughout my doctoral studies.

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